

Pointwise Weighted Approximation of Functions with Endpoint Singularities by Combinations of Bernstein Operators

WEN-MING LU¹, JIN-PING JIA²

¹School of Science, Hangzhou Dianzi University, Hangzhou, People's Republic of China

²School of Mathematics and Statistics, Tianshui Normal University, People's Republic of China

Abstract. We give direct and inverse theorems for the weighted approximation of functions with endpoint singularities by combinations of Bernstein operators.

1991 Mathematics Subject Classification: Primary 41A10, Secondary 41A17.

Keywords and phrases: Combinations of Bernstein polynomials; Functions with endpoint singularities; Direct and inverse results.

Introduction

The set of all continuous functions, defined on the interval I , is denoted by $C(I)$. For any $f \in C([0, 1])$, the corresponding *Bernstein operators* are defined as follows:

$$B_n(f, x) := \sum_{k=0}^n f\left(\frac{k}{n}\right) p_{n,k}(x),$$

Where

$$p_{n,k}(x) := \binom{n}{k} x^k (1-x)^{n-k}, \quad k = 0, 1, 2, \dots, n, \quad x \in [0, 1].$$

Approximation properties of Bernstein operators have been studied very well (see [2], [3], [5]-[8], [12]-[14], for example). In order to approximate the functions with singularities, Della Vecchia et al. [3] and Yu-Zhao [12] introduced some kinds of *modified Bernstein operators*. Throughout the paper, C denotes a positive constant independent of n and x , which may be different in different cases.

Let

$$w(x) = x^\alpha (1-x)^\beta, \quad \alpha, \beta \geq 0, \quad \alpha + \beta > 0, \quad 0 \leq x \leq 1.$$

and

$$C_w := \{f \in C((0, 1)) : \lim_{x \rightarrow 1} (wf)(x) = \lim_{x \rightarrow 0} (wf)(x) = 0\}.$$

The norm in C_w is defined by $\|wf\|_{C_w} := \|wf\| = \sup_{0 \leq x \leq 1} |(wf)(x)|$. Define

$$W_{w,\lambda}^r := \{f \in C_w : f^{(r-1)} \in A.C.((0, 1)), \|w\varphi^{r\lambda} f^{(r)}\| < \infty\}.$$

For $f \in C_w$, define the *weighted modulus of smoothness* by

$$\omega_{\varphi^\lambda}^r(f, t)_w := \sup_{0 < h \leq t} \{ \|w \Delta_{h\varphi^\lambda}^r f\|_{[16h^2, 1-16h^2]} + \|w \vec{\Delta}_h^r f\|_{[0, 16h^2]} + \|w \overleftarrow{\Delta}_h^r f\|_{[1-16h^2, 1]} \},$$

where

$$\begin{aligned} \Delta_{h\varphi}^r f(x) &= \sum_{k=0}^r (-1)^k \binom{r}{k} f(x + (\frac{r}{2} - k)h\varphi(x)), \\ \vec{\Delta}_h^r f(x) &= \sum_{k=0}^r (-1)^k \binom{r}{k} f(x + (r - k)h), \\ \overleftarrow{\Delta}_h^r f(x) &= \sum_{k=0}^r (-1)^k \binom{r}{k} f(x - kh), \end{aligned}$$

and $\varphi(x) = \sqrt{x(1-x)}$. Della Vecchia *et al.* firstly introduced $B_n^*(f, x)$ and $\bar{B}_n(f, x)$ in [3], where the properties of $B_n^*(f, x)$ and $\bar{B}_n(f, x)$ are studied. Among others, they prove that

$$\begin{aligned} \|w(f - B_n^*(f))\| &\leq C\omega_\varphi^2(f, n^{-1/2}), \quad f \in C_w, \\ \|\bar{w}(f - \bar{B}_n(f))\| &\leq \frac{C}{n^{3/2}} \sum_{k=1}^{[\sqrt{n}]} k^2 \omega_\varphi^2(f, \frac{1}{k})^*_w, \quad f \in C_w, \end{aligned}$$

where $w(x) = x^\alpha(1-x)^\beta$, $\alpha, \beta \geq 0$, $\alpha + \beta > 0$, $0 \leq x \leq 1$. In [11], for any $\alpha, \beta > 0$, $n \geq 2r + \alpha + \beta$, there hold

$$\begin{aligned} \|wB_{n,r}^*(f)\| &\leq C\|wf\|, \quad f \in C_w, \\ \|w(B_{n,r}^*(f) - f)\| &\leq \begin{cases} \frac{C}{n^r} (\|wf\| + \|w\varphi^{2r} f^{(2r)}\|), & f \in W_w^{2r}, \\ C(\omega_\varphi^{2r}(f, n^{-1/2})_w + n^{-r}\|wf\|), & f \in C_w. \end{cases} \\ \|w\varphi^{2r} B_{n,r}^{*(2r)}(f)\| &\leq \begin{cases} Cn^r\|wf\|, & f \in C_w, \\ C(\|wf\| + \|w\varphi^{2r} f^{(2r)}\|), & f \in W_w^{2r}. \end{cases} \end{aligned}$$

and for $0 < \gamma < 2r$,

$$\|w(B_{n,r}^*(f) - f)\| = O(n^{-\gamma/2}) \iff \omega_\varphi^{2r}(f, t)_w = O(t^\gamma).$$

Ditzian and Totik [5] extended this method of combinations and defined the following combinations of Bernstein operators:

$$B_{n,r}(f, x) := \sum_{i=0}^{r-1} C_i(n) B_{n_i}(f, x).$$

with the conditions

(a) $n = n_0 < n_1 < \dots < n_{r-1} \leq Cn$,

(b) $\sum_{i=0}^{r-1} |C_i(n)| \leq C$,

(c) $\sum_{i=0}^{r-1} C_i(n) = 1$,

(d) $\sum_{i=0}^{r-1} C_i(n)n_i^{-k} = 0$, for $k = 1, \dots, r - 1$.

2. THE MAIN RESULTS

Now, we can define our *new combinations of Bernstein operators* as follows:

(2.1)
$$B_{n,r}^*(f, x) := B_{n,r}(F_n, x) = \sum_{i=0}^{r-1} C_i(n)B_{n_i}(F_n, x),$$

where $C_i(n)$ satisfy the conditions (a)-(d). For the details, it can be referred to [11]. Our main results are the following:

Theorem 2.1. *If $\alpha, \beta > 0$, for any $f \in C_w$, we have*

(2.2)
$$\|wB_{n,r-1}^{*(r)}(f)\| \leq Cn^r \|wf\|.$$

Theorem 2.2. *For any $\alpha, \beta > 0, 0 \leq \lambda \leq 1$, we have*

(2.3)
$$|w(x)\varphi^{r\lambda}(x)B_{n,r-1}^{*(r)}(f, x)| \leq \begin{cases} Cn^{r/2}\{\max\{n^{r(1-\lambda)/2}, \varphi^{r(\lambda-1)}(x)\}\|wf\|, & f \in C_w, \\ C\|w\varphi^{r\lambda}f^{(r)}\|, & f \in W_{w,\lambda}^r. \end{cases}$$

Theorem 2.3. *For $f \in C_w, \alpha, \beta > 0, \alpha_0 \in (0, 2), 0 \leq \lambda \leq 1$, we have*

(2.4)
$$w(x)|f(x) - B_{n,r-1}^*(f, x)| = O((n^{-\frac{1}{2}}\varphi^{-\lambda}(x)\delta_n(x))^{\alpha_0}) \iff \omega_{\varphi^\lambda}^r(f, t)_w = O(t^{\alpha_0}).$$

3. LEMMAS

Lemma 3.1. ([13]) *For any non-negative real u and v , we have*

(3.1)
$$\sum_{k=1}^{n-1} \left(\frac{k}{n}\right)^{-u} \left(1 - \frac{k}{n}\right)^{-v} p_{n,k}(x) \leq Cx^{-u}(1-x)^{-v}.$$

Lemma 3.2. ([3]) *If $\gamma \in R$, then*

(3.2)
$$\sum_{k=0}^n |k - nx|^\gamma p_{n,k}(x) \leq Cn^{\frac{\gamma}{2}}\varphi^\gamma(x).$$

Lemma 3.3. *For any $f \in W_{w,\lambda}^r, 0 \leq \lambda \leq 1$ and $\alpha, \beta > 0$, we have*

(3.3)
$$\|w\varphi^{r\lambda}F_n^{(r)}\| \leq C\|w\varphi^{r\lambda}f^{(r)}\|.$$

Proof. By symmetry, we only prove the above result when $x \in (0, 1/2]$, the others can be done similarly. Obviously, when $x \in (0, 1/n]$, by [5], we have

$$\begin{aligned} |L_r^{(r)}(f, x)| &\leq C|\vec{\Delta}_{\frac{1}{r}}^r f(0)| \leq Cn^{-\frac{r}{2}+1} \int_0^{\frac{r}{n}} u^{\frac{r}{2}} |f^{(r)}(u)| du \\ &\leq Cn^{-\frac{r}{2}+1} \|w\varphi^{r\lambda}f^{(r)}\| \int_0^{\frac{r}{n}} u^{\frac{r}{2}} w^{-1}(u)\varphi^{-r\lambda}(u) du. \end{aligned}$$

So

$$|w(x)\varphi^{r\lambda}(x)F_n^{(r)}(x)| \leq C\|w\varphi^{r\lambda}f^{(r)}\|.$$

If $x \in [\frac{1}{n}, \frac{2}{n}]$, we have

$$|w(x)\varphi^{r\lambda}(x)F_n^{(r)}(x)| \leq |w(x)\varphi^{r\lambda}(x)f^{(r)}(x)| + |w(x)\varphi^{r\lambda}(x)(f(x) - F_n(x))^{(r)}| \\ := I_1 + I_2.$$

For I_2 , we have

$$f(x) - F_n(x) = (\psi(nx - 1) + 1)(f(x) - L_r(f, x)).$$

$$w(x)\varphi^{r\lambda}(x)|(f(x) - F_n(x))^{(r)}| = w(x)\varphi^{r\lambda}(x) \sum_{i=0}^r n^i |(f(x) - L_r(f, x))^{(r-i)}|.$$

By [5], then

$$|(f(x) - L_r(f, x))^{(r-i)}|_{[\frac{1}{n}, \frac{2}{n}]} \leq C(n^{r-i}\|f - L_r\|_{[\frac{1}{n}, \frac{2}{n}]} + n^{-i}\|f^{(r)}\|_{[\frac{1}{n}, \frac{2}{n}]}), \quad 0 < j < r.$$

Now, we estimate

$$(3.4) \quad I := w(x)\varphi^{r\lambda}(x)|f(x) - L_r(x)|.$$

By Taylor expansion, we have

$$(3.5) \quad f\left(\frac{i}{n}\right) = \sum_{u=0}^{r-1} \frac{\left(\frac{i}{n} - x\right)^u}{u!} f^{(u)}(x) + \frac{1}{(r-1)!} \int_x^{\frac{i}{n}} \left(\frac{i}{n} - s\right)^{r-1} f^{(r)}(s) ds,$$

It follows from (3.5) and the identities

$$\sum_{i=1}^r \left(\frac{i}{n}\right)^v l_i(x) = Cx^v, \quad v = 0, 1, \dots, r.$$

We have

$$L_r(f, x) = \sum_{i=1}^r \sum_{u=0}^{r-1} \frac{\left(\frac{i}{n} - x\right)^u}{u!} f^{(u)}(x) l_i(x) + \frac{1}{(r-1)!} \sum_{i=1}^r l_i(x) \int_x^{\frac{i}{n}} \left(\frac{i}{n} - s\right)^{r-1} f^{(r)}(s) ds \\ = f(x) + \sum_{u=1}^{r-1} f^{(u)}(x) \left(\sum_{v=0}^u C_u^v (-x)^{u-v} \sum_{i=1}^r \left(\frac{i}{n}\right)^v l_i(x) \right) \\ + \frac{1}{(r-1)!} \sum_{i=1}^r l_i(x) \int_x^{\frac{i}{n}} \left(\frac{i}{n} - s\right)^{r-1} f^{(r)}(s) ds,$$

which implies that

$$w(x)\varphi^{r\lambda}(x)|f(x) - L_r(f, x)| = \frac{1}{r!} w(x)\varphi^{r\lambda}(x) \sum_{i=1}^r l_i(x) \int_x^{\frac{i}{n}} \left(\frac{i}{n} - s\right)^{r-1} f^{(r)}(s) ds,$$

since $|l_i(x)| \leq C$ for $x \in [0, \frac{2}{n}]$, $i = 1, 2, \dots, r$.

It follows from $\frac{|\frac{i}{n}-s|^{r-1}}{w(s)} \leq \frac{|\frac{i}{n}-x|^{r-1}}{w(x)}$, s between $\frac{i}{n}$ and x , then

$$\begin{aligned} w(x)\varphi^{r\lambda}(x)|f(x) - L_r(f, x)| &\leq Cw(x)\varphi^{r\lambda}(x) \sum_{i=1}^r \int_x^{\frac{i}{n}} (\frac{i}{n} - s)^{r-1} |f^{(r)}(s)| ds \\ &\leq C\varphi^{r\lambda}(x) \|w\varphi^{r\lambda} f^{(r)}\| \sum_{i=1}^r \int_x^{\frac{i}{n}} (\frac{i}{n} - s)^{r-1} \varphi^{-r\lambda}(s) ds \\ &\leq \frac{C}{n^r} \|w\varphi^{r\lambda} f^{(r)}\|. \end{aligned}$$

Thus

$$I \leq C \|w\varphi^{r\lambda} f^{(r)}\|.$$

So, we get

$$I_2 \leq C \|w\varphi^{r\lambda} f^{(r)}\|.$$

Above all, we have

$$|w(x)\varphi^{r\lambda}(x)F_n^{(r)}(x)| \leq C \|w\varphi^{r\lambda} f^{(r)}\|.$$

□

Lemma 3.4. If $f \in W_{w,\lambda}^r$, $0 \leq \lambda \leq 1$ and $\alpha, \beta > 0$, then

$$(3.6) \quad |w(x)(f(x) - L_r(f, x))|_{[0, \frac{2}{n}]} \leq C \left(\frac{\delta_n(x)}{\sqrt{n}\varphi^\lambda(x)}\right)^r \|w\varphi^{r\lambda} f^{(r)}\|.$$

$$(3.7) \quad |w(x)(f(x) - R_r(f, x))|_{[1-\frac{2}{n}, 1]} \leq C \left(\frac{\delta_n(x)}{\sqrt{n}\varphi^\lambda(x)}\right)^r \|w\varphi^{r\lambda} f^{(r)}\|.$$

Proof. By Taylor expansion, we have

$$(3.8) \quad f\left(\frac{i}{n}\right) = \sum_{u=0}^{r-1} \frac{(\frac{i}{n} - x)^u}{u!} f^{(u)}(x) + \frac{1}{r!} \int_x^{\frac{i}{n}} (\frac{i}{n} - s)^{r-1} f^{(r)}(s) ds,$$

It follows from (3.8) and the identities

$$\sum_{i=1}^{r-1} \left(\frac{i}{n}\right)^v l_i(x) = Cx^v, \quad v = 0, 1, \dots, r.$$

We have

$$\begin{aligned} L_r(f, x) &= \sum_{i=1}^r \sum_{u=0}^{r-1} \frac{(\frac{i}{n} - x)^u}{u!} f^{(u)}(x) l_i(x) + \frac{1}{(r-1)!} \sum_{i=1}^r l_i(x) \int_x^{\frac{i}{n}} (\frac{i}{n} - s)^{r-1} f^{(r)}(s) ds \\ &= f(x) + \sum_{u=1}^{r-1} f^{(u)}(x) \left(\sum_{v=0}^u C_u^v (-x)^{u-v} \sum_{i=1}^r \left(\frac{i}{n}\right)^v l_i(x) \right) \\ &\quad + \frac{1}{(r-1)!} \sum_{i=1}^r l_i(x) \int_x^{\frac{i}{n}} (\frac{i}{n} - s)^{r-1} f^{(r)}(s) ds, \end{aligned}$$

which implies that

$$w(x)|f(x) - L_r(f, x)| = \frac{1}{(r-1)!}w(x) \sum_{i=1}^r l_i(x) \int_x^{\frac{i}{n}} (\frac{i}{n} - s)^{r-1} f^{(r)}(s) ds,$$

since $|l_i(x)| \leq C$ for $x \in [0, \frac{2}{n}]$, $i = 1, 2, \dots, r$.

It follows from $\frac{|\frac{i}{n}-s|^{r-1}}{w(s)} \leq \frac{|\frac{i}{n}-x|^{r-1}}{w(x)}$, s between $\frac{i}{n}$ and x , then

$$\begin{aligned} w(x)|f(x) - L_r(f, x)| &\leq Cw(x) \sum_{i=1}^r \int_x^{\frac{i}{n}} (\frac{i}{n} - s)^{r-1} |f^{(r)}(s)| ds \\ &\leq C \frac{\varphi^r(x)}{\varphi^{r\lambda}(x)} \|w\varphi^{r\lambda} f^{(r)}\| \sum_{i=1}^r \int_x^{\frac{i}{n}} (\frac{i}{n} - s)^{r-1} \varphi^{-r}(s) ds \\ &\leq C \frac{\delta_n^r(x)}{\varphi^{r\lambda}(x)} \|w\varphi^{r\lambda} f^{(r)}\| \sum_{i=1}^r \int_x^{\frac{i}{n}} (\frac{i}{n} - s)^{r-1} \varphi^{-r}(s) ds \\ &\leq C \left(\frac{\delta_n(x)}{\sqrt{n}\varphi^\lambda(x)}\right)^r \|w\varphi^{r\lambda} f^{(r)}\|. \end{aligned}$$

The proof of (3.7) can be done similarly. □

Lemma 3.5. ([11]) For every $\alpha, \beta > 0$, we have

$$(3.9) \quad \|wB_{n,r-1}^*(f)\| \leq C\|wf\|.$$

Lemma 3.6. ([15]) If $\varphi(x) = \sqrt{x(1-x)}$, $0 \leq \lambda \leq 1$, $0 \leq \beta \leq 1$, then

$$(3.10) \quad \int_{-\frac{h\varphi^\lambda(x)}{2}}^{\frac{h\varphi^\lambda(x)}{2}} \cdots \int_{-\frac{h\varphi^\lambda(x)}{2}}^{\frac{h\varphi^\lambda(x)}{2}} \varphi^{-r\beta} \left(x + \sum_{k=1}^r u_k\right) du_1 \cdots du_r \leq Ch^r \varphi^{r(\lambda-\beta)}(x).$$

4. PROOF OF THEOREMS

4.1. Proof of Theorem 2.1. By symmetry, in what follows we will always assume that $x \in (0, \frac{1}{2}]$. It is sufficient to prove the validity for $B_{n,r-1}(F_n, x)$

instead of $B_{n,r-1}^*(f, x)$. When $x \in (0, \frac{1}{n})$, we have

$$\begin{aligned}
 |w(x)B_{n,r-1}^{*(r)}(f, x)| &\leq w(x) \sum_{i=0}^{r-2} \frac{n_i!}{(n_i-r)!} \sum_{k=0}^{n_i-r} |\overrightarrow{\Delta}_{\frac{1}{n_i}}^r F_n(\frac{k}{n_i})| p_{n_i-r,k}(x) \\
 &\leq Cw(x) \sum_{i=0}^{r-2} n_i^r \sum_{k=0}^{n_i-r} |\overrightarrow{\Delta}_{\frac{1}{n_i}}^r F_n(\frac{k}{n_i})| p_{n_i-r,k}(x) \\
 &\leq Cw(x) \sum_{i=0}^{r-2} n_i^r \sum_{k=0}^{n_i-r} \sum_{j=0}^r C_r^j |F_n(\frac{k+r-j}{n_i})| p_{n_i-r,k}(x) \\
 &\leq Cw(x) \sum_{i=0}^{r-2} n_i^r \sum_{j=0}^r C_r^j |F_n(\frac{r-j}{n_i})| p_{n_i-r,0}(x) \\
 &\quad + Cw(x) \sum_{i=0}^{r-2} n_i^r \sum_{j=0}^r C_r^j |F_n(\frac{n_i-j}{n_i})| p_{n_i-r,n_i-r}(x) \\
 &\quad + Cw(x) \sum_{i=0}^{r-2} n_i^r \sum_{k=1}^{n_i-r-1} \sum_{j=0}^r C_r^j |F_n(\frac{k+r-j}{n_i})| p_{n_i-r,k}(x) \\
 &\qquad\qquad\qquad := H_1 + H_2 + H_3.
 \end{aligned}$$

We have

$$\begin{aligned}
 H_1 &\leq Cw(x) \|wf\| \sum_{i=0}^{r-2} n_i^r w^{-1}(\frac{1}{n_i}) p_{n_i-r,0}(x) \\
 &\leq C \|wf\| \sum_{i=0}^{r-2} n_i^r (n_i x)^\alpha (1-x)^{n_i-r} \\
 &\leq Cn^r \|wf\|.
 \end{aligned}$$

When $1 \leq k \leq n_i - r - 1$, we have $1 \leq k + 2r - j \leq n_i - 1$, and thus

$$\frac{w(\frac{k}{n_i-r})}{w(\frac{k+r-j}{n_i})} = (\frac{n_i}{n_i-r})^{\alpha+\beta} (\frac{k}{k+r-j})^\alpha (\frac{n_i-r-k}{n_i-r-k+j})^\beta \leq C.$$

Thereof, by (3.1), we have

$$\begin{aligned}
 H_3 &\leq Cw(x) \|wF_n\| \sum_{i=0}^{r-2} n_i^r \sum_{k=1}^{n_i-r-1} \sum_{j=0}^r \frac{1}{w(\frac{k+r-j}{n_i})} p_{n_i-r,k}(x) \\
 &\leq Cw(x) \|wF_n\| \sum_{i=0}^{r-2} n_i^r \sum_{k=1}^{n_i-r-1} \frac{1}{w(\frac{k}{n_i-r})} p_{n_i-r,k}(x) \\
 &\leq Cn^r \|wF_n\| \leq Cn^r \|wf\|.
 \end{aligned}$$

Similarly, we can get $H_2 \leq Cn^r \|wf\|$. So

$$(4.1) \quad |w(x)B_{n,r-1}^{*(r)}(f, x)| \leq Cn^r \|wf\|, \quad x \in (0, \frac{1}{n}).$$

When $x \in [\frac{1}{n}, \frac{1}{2}]$, according to [5], we have

$$\begin{aligned} & |w(x)B_{n,r-1}^{*(r)}(f, x)| \\ &= |w(x)B_{n,r-1}^{(r)}(F_n, x)| \\ &\leq w(x)(\varphi^2(x))^{-r} \sum_{i=0}^{r-2} \sum_{j=0}^r |Q_j(x, n_i)| n_i^j \sum_{k=0}^{n_i} |(x - \frac{k}{n_i})^j F_n(\frac{k}{n_i})| p_{n_i, k}(x). \end{aligned}$$

Then

$Q_j(x, n_i) = (n_i x(1-x))^{\lfloor \frac{r-j}{2} \rfloor}$, and $(\varphi^2(x))^{-r} Q_j(x, n_i) n_i^j \leq C(n_i/\varphi^2(x))^{\frac{r+j}{2}}$, we have

$$(4.2) \quad \begin{aligned} |w(x)B_{n,r-1}^{*(r)}(f, x)| &\leq Cw(x) \sum_{i=0}^{r-2} \sum_{j=0}^r (\frac{n_i}{\varphi^2(x)})^{\frac{r+j}{2}} \sum_{k=0}^{n_i} |(x - \frac{k}{n_i})^j F_n(\frac{k}{n_i})| p_{n_i, k}(x) \\ &\leq C \|wF_n\| w(x) \sum_{i=0}^{r-2} \sum_{j=0}^r (\frac{n_i}{\varphi^2(x)})^{\frac{r+j}{2}} \sum_{k=0}^{n_i} \frac{|x - \frac{k}{n_i}|^j}{w(\frac{k^*}{n_i})} p_{n_i, k}(x), \end{aligned}$$

where $k^* = 1$ for $k = 0$, $k^* = n_i - 1$ for $k = n_i$ and $k^* = k$ for $1 < k < n_i$. Note that

$$w^2(x) \frac{p_{n_i, 0}(x)}{w^2(\frac{1}{n_i})} \leq C(n_i x)^{2\alpha} (1-x)^{n_i} \leq C,$$

and

$$w^2(x) \frac{p_{n_i, n_i}(x)}{w^2(1 - \frac{1}{n_i})} \leq Cn_i^\beta x^{n_i} \leq C \frac{n_i^\beta}{2^{n_i}} \leq C.$$

By (3.1), we have

$$(4.3) \quad \sum_{k=0}^{n_i} \frac{1}{w^2(\frac{k^*}{n_i})} p_{n_i, k}(x) \leq Cw^{-2}(x).$$

Now, applying Cauchy's inequality, by (3.2) and (4.3), we have

$$\begin{aligned} \sum_{k=0}^{n_i} \frac{|x - \frac{k}{n_i}|^j}{w(\frac{k^*}{n_i})} p_{n_i, k}(x) &\leq (\sum_{k=0}^{n_i} |x - \frac{k}{n_i}|^{2j} p_{n_i, k}(x))^{1/2} (\sum_{k=0}^{n_i} \frac{1}{w^2(\frac{k^*}{n_i})} p_{n_i, k}(x))^{1/2} \\ &\leq Cn_i^{-j/2} \varphi^j(x) w^{-1}(x). \end{aligned}$$

Substituting this to (4.2), we have

$$(4.4) \quad |w(x)B_{n,r-1}^{*(r)}(f, x)| \leq Cn^r \|wf\|, \quad x \in [\frac{1}{n}, \frac{1}{2}].$$

We get Theorem 2.1 by (4.1) and (4.4). \square

4.2. Proof of Theorem 2.2. (1) When $f \in C_w$, we proceed it as follows:

Case 1. If $0 \leq \varphi(x) \leq \frac{1}{\sqrt{n}}$, by (2.2), we have

$$(4.5) \quad |w(x)\varphi^{r\lambda}(x)B_{n,r-1}^{*(r)}(f, x)| \leq Cn^{-r\lambda/2}|w(x)B_{n,r-1}^{*(r)}(f, x)| \leq Cn^{r(1-\lambda/2)}\|wf\|.$$

Case 2. If $\varphi(x) > \frac{1}{\sqrt{n}}$, we have

$$\begin{aligned} & |B_{n,r-1}^{*(r)}(f, x)| = |B_{n,r-1}^{(r)}(F_n, x)| \\ & \leq (\varphi^2(x))^{-r} \sum_{i=0}^{r-2} \sum_{j=0}^r |Q_j(x, n_i)C_i(n)| n_i^j \sum_{k=0}^{n_i} |(x - \frac{k}{n_i})^j F_n(\frac{k}{n_i})| p_{n_i,k}(x), \end{aligned}$$

$Q_j(x, n_i) = (n_i x(1-x))^{\lfloor \frac{r-j}{2} \rfloor}$, and $(\varphi^2(x))^{-2r} Q_j(x, n_i) n_i^j \leq C(n_i/\varphi^2(x))^{\frac{r+j}{2}}$.
So

$$(4.6) \quad \begin{aligned} & |w(x)\varphi^{r\lambda}(x)B_{n,r-1}^{*(r)}(f, x)| \\ & \leq Cw(x)\varphi^{r\lambda}(x) \sum_{i=0}^{r-2} \sum_{j=0}^r (\frac{n_i}{\varphi^2(x)})^{\frac{r+j}{2}} \sum_{k=0}^{n_i} |(x - \frac{k}{n_i})^j F_n(\frac{k}{n_i})| p_{n_i,k}(x) \\ & \leq Cn^{\frac{r}{2}}\varphi^{r(\lambda-1)}(x). \end{aligned}$$

It follows from combining with (4.5) and (4.6) that the first inequality is proved.

(2) When $f \in W_{w,\lambda}^r$, we have

$$(4.7) \quad B_{n,r-1}^{(r)}(F_n, x) = \sum_{i=0}^{r-2} C_i(n)n_i^r \sum_{k=0}^{n_i-r} \vec{\Delta}_{\frac{1}{n_i}}^r F_n(\frac{k}{n_i}) p_{n_i-r,k}(x).$$

If $0 < k < n_i - r$, we have

$$(4.8) \quad |\vec{\Delta}_{\frac{1}{n_i}}^r F_n(\frac{k}{n_i})| \leq Cn_i^{-r+1} \int_0^{\frac{r}{n_i}} |F_n^{(r)}(\frac{k}{n_i} + u)| du,$$

If $k = 0$, we have

$$(4.9) \quad |\vec{\Delta}_{\frac{1}{n_i}}^r F_n(0)| \leq C \int_0^{\frac{r}{n_i}} u^{r-1} |F_n^{(r)}(u)| du,$$

Similarly

$$(4.10) \quad |\vec{\Delta}_{\frac{1}{n_i}}^r F_n(\frac{n_i-r}{n_i})| \leq Cn_i^{-r+1} \int_{1-\frac{r}{n_i}}^1 (1-u)^{\frac{r}{2}} |F_n^{(r)}(u)| du.$$

By (4.7)-(4.10), we have

$$(4.11) \quad \begin{aligned} & |w(x)\varphi^{r\lambda}(x)B_{n,r-1}^{*(r)}(f, x)| \\ & \leq Cw(x)\varphi^{r\lambda}(x)\|w\varphi^{r\lambda}F_n^{(r)}\| \sum_{i=0}^{r-2} \sum_{k=0}^{n_i-r} (w\varphi^{r\lambda})^{-1}\left(\frac{k^*}{n_i}\right)p_{n_i-r,k}(x), \end{aligned}$$

where $k^* = 1$ for $k = 0$, $k^* = n_i - r - 1$ for $k = n_i - r$ and $k^* = k$ for $1 < k < n_i - r$. By (3.1), we have

$$(4.12) \quad \sum_{k=0}^{n_i-r} (w\varphi^{r\lambda})^{-1}\left(\frac{k^*}{n_i}\right)p_{n_i-r,k}(x) \leq C(w\varphi^{r\lambda})^{-1}(x).$$

which combining with (4.12) give

$$|w(x)\varphi^{r\lambda}(x)B_{n,r-1}^{*(r)}(f, x)| \leq C\|w\varphi^{r\lambda}f^{(r)}\|. \square$$

So we get the second inequality of the Theorem 2.2.

4.3. Proof of Theorem 2.3.

4.3.1. *The direct theorem.* We know

$$(4.13) \quad \begin{aligned} F_n(t) &= F_n(x) + F_n'(t)(t-x) + \dots + \frac{1}{(r-1)!} \int_x^t (t-u)^{r-1} f^{(r)}(u) du, \\ (4.14) \quad B_{n,r-1}((\cdot-x)^k, x) &= 0, \quad k = 1, 2, \dots, r-1. \end{aligned}$$

According to the definition of $W_{w,\lambda}^r$, for any $g \in W_{w,\lambda}^r$, we have $B_{n,r-1}^*(g, x) = B_{n,r-1}(G_n(g), x)$, and $w(x)|G_n(x) - B_{n,r-1}(G_n, x)| = w(x)|B_{n,r-1}(R_r(G_n, t, x), x)|$, thereof $R_r(G_n, t, x) = \int_x^t (t-u)^{r-1} G_n^{(r)}(u) du$. It follows from $\frac{|t-u|^{r-1}}{w(u)} \leq \frac{|t-x|^{r-1}}{w(x)}$, u between t and x , we have

$$(4.15) \quad \begin{aligned} w(x)|G_n(x) - B_{n,r-1}(G_n, x)| &\leq C\|w\varphi^{r\lambda}G_n^{(r)}\|w(x)B_{n,r-1}\left(\int_x^t \frac{|t-u|^{r-1}}{w(u)\varphi^{r\lambda}(u)} du, x\right) \\ &\leq C\|w\varphi^{r\lambda}G_n^{(r)}\|w(x)\left(B_{n,r-1}\left(\int_x^t \frac{|t-u|^{r-1}}{\varphi^{2r\lambda}(u)} du, x\right)\right)^{\frac{1}{2}} \\ &\quad \left(B_{n,r-1}\left(\int_x^t \frac{|t-u|^{r-1}}{w^2(u)} du, x\right)\right)^{\frac{1}{2}}. \end{aligned}$$

also

$$(4.16) \quad \int_x^t \frac{|t-u|^{r-1}}{\varphi^{2r\lambda}(u)} du \leq C \frac{|t-x|^r}{\varphi^{2r\lambda}(x)}, \quad \int_x^t \frac{|t-u|^{r-1}}{w^2(u)} du \leq \frac{|t-x|^r}{w^2(x)}.$$

By (3.2), (4.15) and (4.16), we have

$$\begin{aligned}
 w(x)|G_n(x) - B_{n,r-1}(G_n, x)| &\leq C\|w\varphi^{r\lambda}G_n^{(r)}\|\varphi^{-r\lambda}(x)B_{n,r-1}(|t-x|^r, x) \\
 &\leq Cn^{-\frac{r}{2}}\frac{\varphi^r(x)}{\varphi^{r\lambda}(x)}\|w\varphi^{r\lambda}G_n^{(r)}\| \\
 &\leq Cn^{-\frac{r}{2}}\frac{\delta_n^r(x)}{\varphi^{r\lambda}(x)}\|w\varphi^{r\lambda}G_n^{(r)}\| \\
 (4.17) \qquad \qquad \qquad &= C\left(\frac{\delta_n(x)}{\sqrt{n}\varphi^\lambda(x)}\right)^r\|w\varphi^{r\lambda}G_n^{(r)}\|.
 \end{aligned}$$

By (3.3), (3.6), (3.7) and (4.17), when $g \in W_{w,\lambda}^r$, then

$$\begin{aligned}
 w(x)|g(x) - B_{n,r-1}^*(g, x)| &\leq w(x)|g(x) - G_n(g, x)| + w(x)|G_n(g, x) - B_{n,r-1}^*(g, x)| \\
 &\leq |w(x)(g(x) - L_r(g, x))|_{[0, \frac{2}{n}]} + |w(x)(g(x) - R_r(g, x))|_{[1-\frac{2}{n}, 1]} \\
 &\qquad \qquad \qquad + C\left(\frac{\delta_n(x)}{\sqrt{n}\varphi^\lambda(x)}\right)^r\|w\varphi^{r\lambda}G_n^{(r)}\| \\
 (4.18) \qquad \qquad \qquad &\leq C\left(\frac{\delta_n(x)}{\sqrt{n}\varphi^\lambda(x)}\right)^r\|w\varphi^{r\lambda}g^{(r)}\|.
 \end{aligned}$$

For $f \in C_w$, we choose proper $g \in W_{w,\lambda}^r$, by (3.9) and (4.18), then

$$\begin{aligned}
 w(x)|f(x) - B_{n,r-1}^*(f, x)| &\leq w(x)|f(x) - g(x)| + w(x)|B_{n,r-1}^*(f - g, x)| \\
 &\qquad \qquad \qquad + w(x)|g(x) - B_{n,r-1}^*(g, x)| \\
 &\leq C(\|w(f - g)\|) + \left(\frac{\delta_n(x)}{\sqrt{n}\varphi^\lambda(x)}\right)^r\|w\varphi^{r\lambda}g^{(r)}\| \\
 &\leq C\omega_{\varphi^\lambda}^r\left(f, \frac{\delta_n(x)}{\sqrt{n}\varphi^\lambda(x)}\right)_w. \square
 \end{aligned}$$

4.3.2. *The inverse theorem.* We define the weighted main-part modulus for $D = R_+$ by

$$\begin{aligned}
 \Omega_{\varphi^\lambda}^r(C, f, t)_w &= \sup_{0 < h \leq t} \|w\Delta_{h\varphi^\lambda}^r f\|_{[Ch^*, \infty)}, \\
 \Omega_{\varphi^\lambda}^r(1, f, t)_w &= \Omega_{\varphi^\lambda}^r(f, t)_w.
 \end{aligned}$$

where $C > 2^{1/\beta(0)-1}$, $\beta(0) > 0$ and h^* is given by

$$h^* = \begin{cases} (Ar)^{1/1-\beta(0)}h^{1/1-\beta(0)}, & 0 \leq \beta(0) < 1, \\ 0, & \beta(0) \geq 1. \end{cases}$$

The main-part K -functional is given by

$$K_{r,\varphi^\lambda}(f, t^r)_w = \sup_{0 < h \leq t} \inf_g \{ \|w(f - g)\|_{[Ch^*, \infty)} + t^r \|w\varphi^{r\lambda}g^{(r)}\|_{[Ch^*, \infty)} \},$$

where $g^{(r-1)} \in A.C.((Ch^*, \infty))$. By ([5]), we have

$$(4.19) \quad C^{-1}\Omega_{\varphi^\lambda}^r(f, t)_w \leq \omega_{\varphi^\lambda}^r(f, t)_w \leq C \int_0^t \frac{\Omega_{\varphi^\lambda}^r(f, \tau)_w}{\tau} d\tau,$$

$$(4.20) \quad C^{-1}K_{r, \varphi^\lambda}(f, t^r)_w \leq \Omega_{\varphi^\lambda}^r(f, t)_w \leq CK_{r, \varphi^\lambda}(f, t^r)_w.$$

Proof. Let $\delta > 0$, by (4.20), we choose proper g so that

$$(4.21) \quad \|w(f - g)\| \leq C\Omega_{\varphi^\lambda}^r(f, \delta)_w, \quad \|w\varphi^{r\lambda} g^{(r)}\| \leq C\delta^{-r}\Omega_{\varphi^\lambda}^r(f, \delta)_w.$$

then

$$(4.22) \quad \begin{aligned} |w(x)\Delta_{h\varphi^\lambda}^r f(x)| &\leq |w(x)\Delta_{h\varphi^\lambda}^r(f(x) - B_{n, r-1}^*(f, x))| + |w(x)\Delta_{h\varphi^\lambda}^r B_{n, r-1}^*(f - g, x)| \\ &\quad + |w(x)\Delta_{h\varphi^\lambda}^r B_{n, r-1}^*(g, x)| \\ &\leq \sum_{j=0}^r C_r^j (n^{-\frac{1}{2}}\delta_n(x + (\frac{r}{2} - j)h\varphi^\lambda(x)))^{\alpha_0} \\ &\quad + \int_{-\frac{h\varphi^\lambda(x)}{2}}^{\frac{h\varphi^\lambda(x)}{2}} \cdots \int_{-\frac{h\varphi^\lambda(x)}{2}}^{\frac{h\varphi^\lambda(x)}{2}} w(x)B_{n, r-1}^{*(r)}(f - g, x + \sum_{k=1}^r u_k) du_1 \cdots du_r \\ &\quad + \int_{-\frac{h\varphi^\lambda(x)}{2}}^{\frac{h\varphi^\lambda(x)}{2}} \cdots \int_{-\frac{h\varphi^\lambda(x)}{2}}^{\frac{h\varphi^\lambda(x)}{2}} w(x)B_{n, r-1}^{*(r)}(g, x + \sum_{k=1}^r u_k) du_1 \cdots du_r \\ &:= J_1 + J_2 + J_3. \end{aligned}$$

Obviously

$$(4.23) \quad J_1 \leq C(n^{-\frac{1}{2}}\delta_n(x))^{\alpha_0}.$$

By (2.2) and (4.21), we have

$$(4.24) \quad \begin{aligned} J_2 &\leq Cn^r \|w(f - g)\| \int_{-\frac{h\varphi^\lambda(x)}{2}}^{\frac{h\varphi^\lambda(x)}{2}} \cdots \int_{-\frac{h\varphi^\lambda(x)}{2}}^{\frac{h\varphi^\lambda(x)}{2}} du_1 \cdots du_r \\ &\leq Cn^r h^r \varphi^{r\lambda}(x) \|w(f - g)\| \\ &\leq Cn^r h^r \varphi^{r\lambda}(x) \Omega_{\varphi^\lambda}^r(f, \delta)_w. \end{aligned}$$

By the first inequality of (2.3), we let $\lambda = 1$, and (3.10) as well as (4.21), we have

$$(4.25) \quad \begin{aligned} J_2 &\leq Cn^{\frac{r}{2}} \|w(f - g)\| \int_{-\frac{h\varphi^\lambda(x)}{2}}^{\frac{h\varphi^\lambda(x)}{2}} \cdots \int_{-\frac{h\varphi^\lambda(x)}{2}}^{\frac{h\varphi^\lambda(x)}{2}} \varphi^{-r}(x + \sum_{k=1}^r u_k) du_1 \cdots du_r \\ &\leq Cn^{\frac{r}{2}} h^r \varphi^{r(\lambda-1)}(x) \|w(f - g)\| \\ &\leq Cn^{\frac{r}{2}} h^r \varphi^{r(\lambda-1)}(x) \Omega_{\varphi^\lambda}^r(f, \delta)_w. \end{aligned}$$

By the second inequality of (2.3) and (4.21), we have

$$\begin{aligned}
 J_3 &\leq C \|w\varphi^{r\lambda} g^{(r)}\| w(x) \int_{-\frac{h\varphi^\lambda(x)}{2}}^{\frac{h\varphi^\lambda(x)}{2}} \cdots \int_{-\frac{h\varphi^\lambda(x)}{2}}^{\frac{h\varphi^\lambda(x)}{2}} w^{-1}\left(x + \sum_{k=1}^r u_k\right) \varphi^{-r\lambda}\left(x + \sum_{k=1}^r u_k\right) du_1 \cdots du_r \\
 &\leq Ch^r \|w\varphi^{r\lambda} g^{(r)}\| \\
 (4.26) \qquad &\leq Ch^r \delta^{-r} \Omega_{\varphi^\lambda}^r(f, \delta)_w.
 \end{aligned}$$

Now, by (4.22)-(4.26), we get

$$|w(x)\Delta_{h\varphi^\lambda}^r f(x)| \leq C\{(n^{-\frac{1}{2}}\delta_n(x))^{\alpha_0} + h^r(n^{-\frac{1}{2}}\delta_n(x))^{-r}\Omega_{\varphi^\lambda}^r(f, \delta)_w + h^r\delta^{-r}\Omega_{\varphi^\lambda}^r(f, \delta)_w\}.$$

When $n \geq 2$, we have

$$n^{-\frac{1}{2}}\delta_n(x) < (n-1)^{-\frac{1}{2}}\delta_{n-1}(x) \leq \sqrt{2}n^{-\frac{1}{2}}\delta_n(x),$$

Choosing proper $x, n \in N$, so that

$$n^{-\frac{1}{2}}\delta_n(x) \leq \delta < (n-1)^{-\frac{1}{2}}\delta_{n-1}(x),$$

Therefore

$$|w(x)\Delta_{h\varphi^\lambda}^r f(x)| \leq C\{\delta^{\alpha_0} + h^r\delta^{-r}\Omega_{\varphi^\lambda}^r(f, \delta)_w\}.$$

By Borens-Lorentz lemma, we get

$$(4.27) \qquad \qquad \qquad \Omega_{\varphi^\lambda}^r(f, t)_w \leq Ct^{\alpha_0}.$$

So, by (4.27), we get

$$\omega_{\varphi^\lambda}^r(f, t)_w \leq C \int_0^t \frac{\Omega_{\varphi^\lambda}^r(f, \tau)_w}{\tau} d\tau = C \int_0^t \tau^{\alpha_0-1} d\tau = Ct^{\alpha_0}.$$

□

References

- [1] P.L. Butzer, Linear combinations of Bernstein polynomials, *Canad. J. Math.* 5 (1953), pp. 559-567.
- [2] H. Berens and G. Lorentz, Inverse theorems for Bernstein polynomials, *Indiana Univ. Math. J.* 21 (1972), pp. 693-708.
- [3] D. Della Vechhia, G. Mastroianni and J. Szabados, Weighted approximation of functions with endpoint and inner singularities by Bernstein operators, *Acta Math. Hungar.* 103 (2004), pp. 19-41.
- [4] Z. Ditzian, A global inverse theorem for combinations of Bernstein polynomials, *J. Approx. Theory* 26 (1979), pp. 277-292.
- [5] Z. Ditzian and V. Totik, *Moduli of Smoothness*, Springer-Verlag, Berlin, New York (1987).
- [6] S.S. Guo, C.X. Li and X.W. Liu, Pointwise approximation for linear combinations of Bernstein operators, *J. Approx. Theory* 107 (2000), pp. 109-120.
- [7] S.S. Guo, H. Tong and G. Zhang, Pointwise weighted approximation by Bernstein operators, *Acta Math. Hungar.* 101 (2003), pp. 293-311.
- [8] G.G. Lorentz, *Bernstein Polynomial*, University of Toronto Press, Toronto (1953).

- [9] L.S. Xie, Pointwise simultaneous approximation by combinations of Bernstein operators, *J. Approx. Theory* 137 (2005), pp. 1-21.
- [10] L.S. Xie, The saturation class for linear combinations of Bernstein operators, *Arch. Math.* 91 (2008), pp. 86-96.
- [11] D.S. Yu, weighted approximation of functions with singularities by combinations of Bernstein operators, *J. Applied Mathematics and Computation.* 206(2008), pp.906-918.
- [12] D.S. Yu and D.J. Zhao, Approximation of functions with singularities by truncated Bernstein operators, *Southeast Bull. Math.* 30 (2006), pp. 1178-1189.
- [13] D.X. Zhou, Rate of convergence for Bernstein operators with Jacobi weights, *Acta Math. Sinica* 35 (1992), pp. 331-338.
- [14] D.X. Zhou, On smoothness characterized by Bernstein type operators, *J. Approx. Theory* 81 (1994), pp. 303-315.
- [15] J.J. Zhang, Z.B. Xu, Direct and inverse approximation theorems with Jacobi weight for combinations and higher derivatives of Baskakov operators(in Chinese), *Journal of systems science and mathematical sciences.* 2008 28 (1), pp. 30-39.